

REGIONAL DISPARITIES OF RED COLLAR WORKERS IN SOLAPUR DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT:

Human activities which are performed in exchange for money or money's worth are called economic activities. There are four types of economic activities which include primary, secondary, tertiary and quaternary economic activities. Among them primary economic activities are basically determine the socio-economic disparities in any rural area of India. The term “Red Collar workers” denotes the workers who are engaged in primary economic activities. Agriculture, hunting and gathering, pastoral activities, fishing, forestry, mining and quarrying are the example of these activities. Agriculture is one of the significant economic activities which plays the vital role in any region which determine the socio-economic disparities.

In Solapur district, there were 78.06 percent of people were engaged in primary economic activities in 1991 and it decreased by 13.11 in 2014. Other hand 3.85 percent agricultural area decreased during investigation period because the burden of population on agricultural land and increase the industrial sector basically. But the irrigated are were increased by 14.52 percent in 2014.

KEY WORDS: Red collar, MSL, Livelihood, Good Change, TFDO, DFD, GDP

INTRODUCTION:

Broadly speaking, India is an agricultural country which plays vital role in India's economy. About 58 percent of the rural households in India depend on agriculture as their principal means of livelihood. Agricultural and its development is largely determined by various physical and socio-economic factors such as relief, climate, drainage pattern, soils, irrigation, population, transport and communication etc. These factors influence the agriculture in many ways and determine the extent of risk in overall development of agriculture. Some aspects of farming systems are also influenced by the socio-economic factors. All factors of physical and socio-economic work together and bring results, or impact on overall growth of agriculture. In Solapur district Mangalwedha tahsil observed highest percent of red collar workers in 1991 and 2014, because of the good indices of soil moisture for jowar and other crops. In study region Barshi has recorded highest number of percentage change in primary economics activity and Madha recorded lowest number of percentage change in primary economics activities in the study period. It means that the Barshi tahsil has good represent in transformation of economics activities from primary to other economic activity. The lowest percentage of people are engaged in primary sector were in North Solapur which contribute only 15.59 percentage in 1990-91 and 14.52 percentage in 2013-14.

OBJECTIVES:

The specific objectives of present studies are as follows.

1. To know the regional distribution of Red collar workers in Solapur district.
2. To know the spatial disparities in regional development in study region.

STUDY REGION:

Solapur district lies to the south western part of Maharashtra state which is the fifth largest district in terms of area and seventh largest in terms of population in Maharashtra. The Solapur district is located between 17°07' N to 18° 33' N latitudes and 74°37' E to 76°26' E longitudes. The average height of Solapur district from MSL varies from 500 to 800 meters. It is bounded by Sangli district to its southwest, Satara district to its west, Pune district to its northwest, Ahmadnagar district to its north, Osmanabad district to its east and Bijapur district in the Karnataka to the south. The total geographical area of study region is 14,895 sq. km. with a population of 4,31,7756 according to 2011 census. For administrative purpose Solapur district is divided in to 11 tahsils i.e. Akkalkot, Barshi, Karmala, Madha, Malshiras, Mangalwedha, Mohol, North Solapur, Pandharpur, Sangola and South Solapur and constitutes 20 percent of the total geographical area of Pune division and 4.8 percent of the state of Maharashtra.

DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY:

As the study has carried out by using primary as well as secondary sources of data. There have been various publications and reports on social and economic sectors in Solapur district and information have been collected from Census of India, Maharashtra, Series-28 Part-XII-B, District Census Handbook Solapur. Daily Lokmat News Paper, Daily Sakal News Paper, District Statistical Review of Solapur district, Socio-Economic Abstract of Solapur district, 1991 and 2014. Due to the unavailable of data the nearest years data is used for the determine the regional disparities.

For the determining the regional disparities of red collars workers in Solapur district and interrelationships of the social and economic development have been explained by using statistical techniques Z score test. Following formula was used for calculation.

$$Z_i = \frac{X_i - \text{Mean}}{SD}$$

Where,

X= standardized random variable

Mean= average of data

SD= standard deviation

EXPLANATION:

Human population have adopted various types of economic activities as the basic support to these life. These activities are aimed at procuring the sustenance and the luxuries. What activities people adopt in a particular region depends largely upon the physical environment of the region they inhabit. Some area offer the choice of a large number of occupation while others restrict this choice to a few. Which activities are performed with the main motive of learning of earning profit money or livelihood are known are economic

activities. They consist production, purchase, sale, exchange and distribution of goods and services. Some of the people are engaged in production of goods and services. Due to physical and mental inability some people are not participated in the work.

Primary activities are thus concerned with obtaining products from nature directly. Due to outdoor nature of their work, people engaged in these activities are often called red-collar workers. Agriculture, hunting and gathering, pastoral activities, fishing, forestry, mining and quarrying are the example of these activities. Primary economic activities involves the activity of extracting goods from nature, such as agriculture, forestry, fishing and mining. The following graph indicates that the percentage of primary activities in Solapur district in 1991, 2001 and 2014.

1. Agriculture:

Agriculture refers to the activity of raising crops and rearing animals. In the study region agriculture is the main economic activity which is powerful engine of economic development. Today in study region agriculture contribute more than 14 percent to GDP and more than 49 percent of labour force employed in agriculture (*Suryawanshi Santosh, 2013*). Other hand agriculture sector undergoes secular decline relative to other sectors of economic development in study region. It plays an important role in overall development of the region and it provides food surplus to the growing population, raw material to agro-based industries, employment to rural population and improves their standard of living. Agricultural development bring social and cultural changes as increased per capita income in rural areas which increased literacy and level of education. It is clear that all circumstances of agricultural productivity makes important contribution to regional development.

In Solapur district agriculture is main source of people's livelihood. About 49 percent of the working population engaged in the agriculture. The agriculture of this region provides of raw materials for industries like sugarcane, cottage and oil mills. Therefore, agriculture of the Solapur district has got considerable importance in the economic development.

2. Livestock and Forest products:

In India agriculture provides a livelihood for more people than other industry. In developing countries livestock provide one third of agricultural output. Many people in this study region are engaged in the not only agriculture but also livestock. We get various products from the livestock i.e. meat, milk, fiber for clothing, rugs, fine leather etc. livestock also provides organic manure which is useful in the farm for increase the productivity of crops in any region.

For the agricultural operation of ploughing, harrowing, drawing water for irrigation purpose livestock are useful than manpower. Highest number of livestock found in the Malshiras tahsil and lowest number of livestock found North Solapur in both year, due to lowest geographical area. In Malshiras, maximum land is potential, which is useful for the livestock. Other hand the North Solapur is the smallest tahsil in Solapur district and it has low livestock.

In study region highest population of livestock are goats and sheep because, these animal is useful to all purpose and it is easy to handle. In the investigation period the numbers of livestock population were decreased in Solapur district, and it shows that slight change of livestock population at tahsil level. In Solapur district buffalos and cattle are also plays vital role in production of milk, but number of these livestock population decreased in 2013. The

highest number of livestock population observed in Malshiras tahsil in 1991 which were 18.14 percent and it decreased by 2.9 percent in 2013. The lowest livestock population observed in North Solapur tahsil in both year, but its percentage increased in 2013. The highest percent of livestock population was increased in Pandharpur tahsil and lowest percent of livestock population decreased in Akkalkot tahsil.

Forestry constitute an important resource which provides employment to a large number of people. It includes the production of timber and gathering activities of tree products. Gathering of forest products is largely a subsistence activity which, involve collection of food products such as fruits, leaves, tubers, paper and wood etc. It also involve collection of various products for export and preparation of extracts and other products for distribution in wide markets. Dominant forest production is wood which useful in rural area in developing countries. There are limited forest area in Solapur district. Some of the people are engaged in the field of forest products for fuel. Due to small proportion of forest area these activity does not developed in study region in last two decade.

3. Fishing:

Fishing is the primary activities which have declined in economic importance during modern age they still remain important activities in terms of providing employment to a large population. These activities remain important items of foreign trade. In rural area these activities provide source of income in cultivators and agricultural labourers. In study region some of the region are famous for fishing activities. In some of the tahsil fish cultural schemes propagated by the FDO (fish development officers), TFDO (tahsil fisheries development officers) and Gram sevak are now welcomed by people for fish culture. A provision also made to give financial assistance through Panchayat Samiti and DFD (District Fishery Department) in the form of loans. So many co-operative societies engaged in fish culture.

In Solapur district favorable area in form of rivers, tanks and reservoirs under fish culture was 29965 hect. in 1990-91 and it was decreased in 2013-14 which was 27458 hect. Actual area under fish culture was 29965 hect. in the year 1990-91, which was decreased to 26778 in the year 2013-14.

4. Dairy Farming:

Dairy farming plays vital role in agricultural economy in India. The purpose of dairy farming is to provide the milk production to people in reasonable rate and provide the occupation to the farmers. In the study region, there were 1986 milk co-operatives societies in 1990-91 and it increased to 3413 in 2013-14. It means the number of factories increase due to the increasing production of milk in every tahsil. In all tahsil excepting Karmala, Madha and Mohol increase the percentage of number of milk co-operative societies. Total number of members are also slightly increase excepting Madha, Mohol, Pandharpur and Sangola. The collection of milk is decrease excepting Madha, Malshiras and South Solapur tahsil. The total production of milk is increase but the percentage of milk production is decreased in study region.

In 2013-14 there were 3413 co-operatives society, 174089 total number of members

Figure No. 2

and 398560 liter milk production per day. Over a period of 25 year there is double change in collection of total milk production. At present there are 22 cold storage centers are located in the study region having 850000 liters capacity. Madha tahsil observed highest number (4) of cold storage followed by Barshi (3) and North Solapur (3). To take the care of milk animal and other, there are six veterinary hospitals,

121 veterinary dispensaries and 84 primary veterinary health centers located in study region.

The table No. 1, indicate the tahsil wise z-score value of primary activities in Solapur district in 1991 and 2014.

Table No. 1: Solapur District- Primary Economic Activities

Sr. No.	Tahsil	Z-Score Value	
		1991	2014
1	Akkalkot	+0.2639	+0.2493
2	Barshi	-0.1908	-0.3091
3	Karmala	+0.5013	+0.4943
4	Madha	+0.3222	+0.3829
5	Malshiras	+0.2546	+0.3031
6	Mangalwedha	+0.5322	+0.5638
7	Mohol	+0.5145	+0.5362
8	North Solapur	-2.9360	-2.9062
9	Pandharpur	-0.0353	-0.0883
10	Sangola	+0.4194	+0.3730
11	South Solapur	+0.3546	+0.4011

Source: Compiled by the Researcher

The analysis of data using Z-score model reveals that there is marked regional disparities in terms of primary economic activities in Solapur district. It is clear from map that primary economic activities is high in four tahsil in 1991, namely Karmala, Mangalwedha, Mohol and Sangola but in 2014 Sangola tahsil slightly decrease and all remaining tahsil with South Solapur remain in high level. In the category of medium level of primary economic activities development Akkalkot, Madha, Malshiras and South Solapur tahsil have been identified in the year 1991 and Sangola tahsil included in 2014. In the category of low level development of primary economic activities in both year Barshi, North Solapur and Pandharpur tahsil have been identified.

Level of Socio-Economic Development in Primary Economic Activities:

Development is a specified state of growth or advancement; a new and advanced product or idea; an event constituting a new stage in a changing situation. According to Chambers (1997), development is 'Good change' but this is not straightforward as it sounds. It has a history of being linked with capitalism with 'Good Change' associated with industrialization and modernization on the basis of free market. It is a multi-dimensional phenomenon. Some of its major dimensions include i.e. the level of economic growth, level of education, level of health services, degree of modernization, status of women, quality of housing, level of nutrition, distribution of goods and services, and access to communication. The process of socio-economic development in India is not uniform. One of the most important aspects of India's development progress is its remarkable regional disparities in eliminating basic deprivations, which economy suffers from large and incessant inequalities. These inequalities create tensions and conflicts in the society.

Figure No.3

CONCLUSION:

1. Highest percent of workers engaged in primary sector of economy in study region. In this activities agriculture plays an important role in overall development of the region and it is one of the major source for gross income in economy. More than 68 percent of labour force employed in agriculture and it provides employment to rural population, raw material for agro-based industries. Economy of this region based on agriculture and agro-based industries. Therefore, agricultural productivity makes important contribution to regional development.
2. Percentage of agricultural area to total geographical area was 75.99 percent in the year 1990-91, which was decreased to 72.14 percent in the year 2013-14 in study region. Region has good amount of agricultural land but Small decrease of the agricultural land shows the scanty rainfall, lack of use modern technology in agriculture and the change the trend of people towards the agriculture is too witnessed in study region.
3. The percentage of irrigated area to agricultural area was 10.23 in the year 1990-91, which was increased to 24.75 percent in 2013-14. It means that during the investigation period area under irrigation was increased by 14.52 percent. This change of irrigation increased the production of yield per hectare in fruit crops.

4. The study of cropping pattern reveals that area under cereals crop is decreased by 6.49 percent over the period of twenty four years in study region. In the same time area under pulses, fruits, vegetables and other crops also increased. It means that area under cereals and oilseeds crops converted into pulses (+2.91 percent), fruits (+3.43 percent), vegetables (+0.12 percent) and other crops (+9.29 percent). The increase in the area under pulses observed in Akkalkot (16.92 percent), South Solapur (7.03 percent) and Madha (0.58 percent) tahsil. The increase in the area under fruit crops observed in all tahsil of Solapur district. The highest percent of increasing percent observed in Pandharpur (19.46 percent) and Malshiras (11.96 percent) tahsil. All the changes of cropping pattern clearly show that agricultural transformation from subsistence to commercial farming.
5. Percentage of food crops area to gross cropped area was 78.44 percent in 1990-91 which decreased to 66.10 in 2013-14. In this crops jowar, bajara, wheat and maize are important crops in study region. The highest percent of food crops area was observed in Karmala tahsil because of shallow, medium and deep soil observed in Karmala tahsil, which is useful for jowar, bajara, maize and wheat crops. There were eight tahsil in the year 1990-91 which percent of food crops area were more than average percent of Solapur district. In the year 1990-91 the percentage of food crops was lowest in Akkalkot tahsil but it became highest in the 2013-14.
6. Productivity (yield per hectare) of cereals like jowar, wheat, maize, bajara and rice was 537 kg., 1067 kg., 1213kg., 383 kg., and 880 kg. in the year 1990-91 but it was decreased excepting maize in 2013-14 and it was observed 538 kg., 1001 kg., 2210 kg., 347 kg. and 286 kg. respectively. This decreasing trend of cereals crops show the farmers tendency towards food crops were decreased nowadays and they emphasize on cash crops.
7. In cash crops the percentage of area under sugarcane, grapes, pomegranates and vegetables are increased in the investigation period. Other hand area under pulses was increased by 2.91 percent in study region, area under fruits was increased by 3.43 percent and area under vegetables was increased by 0.12 percent. It means the area under cash crops was increasing from last two decade in study region.
8. Livestock occupies important place in rural area of the agro-based economy in the Solapur district. But the livestock population decreased by 24.99 percent in 2013. In the year 1990 total livestock population was 1571072 which decreased to 1178468 in the year 2013. The livestock population was increased in the Pandharpur (3.02 percent), Madha (2.97), Sangola (1.99), Karmala (0.47), Mangalwedha (0.42) and North Solapur (0.29) tahsil.
9. Fish farming also provides source of income to the cultivators and agricultural labourers. The favourable area available for fish culture was 29965 hectares in the year 1990-91 which was decreased to 27458 hectares in the year 2013-14. Actual area under fish culture was same to available area in the year 1990-91 and it also decreased to 26778 hectares in the year 2013-14. Area under fish culture is relatively high in Madha tahsil (68.31 percent) and Akkalkot tahsil has lowest area under fish culture. There were only 76 fish co-operative societies in the year 1990-91 and it increased to 137 in the year 2013-14. The fish production of Solapur district was 1800 metric tonnes in the year 1990-91 and it increased to 2950 metric tonnes in the year 2013-14.

10. Dairy farming also plays vital role in agricultural economy in Solapur district. Number of milk co-operative societies are 1986 with 95231 members and collection of milk was 78684500 liters in the year 1990-91 which increased to 3413 milk co-operative societies, with 174089 members and 145474400 liters in 2013-14. Out of the total milk collection in the district, Malshiras tahsil rank first with 39.45 percent and Sangola tahsil rank second position with 17.75 percent in Solapur district.

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